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INGAME
Gaming for Social Inclusion and Civic Participation

INGAME

INGAME – Gaming for Social Inclusion and Civic Participation – A holistic approach for a cultural shift in education and policy

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National INGAME Ecosystem of Needs, Practices Target Groups, Stakeholders and Mode of Work Report - Spain

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1. Introduction

1.1. Aim/Objectives of Report

The report is developed in the frames of the WP2 “Mapping the INGAME Ecosystem of Needs, Practices Target Groups, Stakeholders and Mode of Work” of the INGAME project.

The project aims at increasing the skills and civic participation of young adults aged between 18 and 35 using an online game called INGAME. It will allow users to learn from the simulated experience by improving critical thinking on social and political circumstances, building new skills and stimulating interest in collective action.

In particular, WP2 is devoted to study the extent of educational, civic participation, social inclusion and gender-sensitivity of policies and programmes in the partner countries, and how online games could reinforce and materialize their scope in outreaching the youth, through a literature review on the topic and a survey conducted among target group and stakeholders.

This report describes and analyses the results of the study in the Spanish context.

The first part of the document “Key findings from Desk Research” analyses the current degree of civic participation of young people in Spain, the active policies in the field of civic engagement, gender equality and social inclusion.

The second part “Research results: questionnaires” analyses the results of three online questionnaires addressed to young people aged between 18 and 35 and to the relative main stakeholders (members of youth organizations, NGOs, voluntary associations, etc.) conducted between April and June 2020.

The “Conclusions and Recommendations” section provides a global summary of the key results of the research and recommendations based on the evidences arisen from the questionnaires. Gaps and issues in existing practices on civic participation, social inclusion and gender equality as so as good practices will allow to better focus on the requirements of the game to be developed.

2. Key findings from Desk Research: the Spanish context

Desk-based research involves the analysis of recent, relevant and available data and resources (literature, reports, policy documents, previous surveys, research studies, etc.) on the pedagogical models for fostering awareness on issues related to social inclusion, gender equality and civic

participation for youth developing intercultural skills and positive attitudes with the use of games in both formal and informal learning environments for youth.

Researchers also pay attention to “good practices” that uses online gaming to raise youth awareness on social inclusion, gender equality and civic participation.

2.1. Literature Review/National Context

Source: <https://eacea.ec.europa.eu/national-policies/en/content/youthwiki/overview-spain#>

Last modified on 26/08/2020

The Spanish Constitution (Constitución Española de 1978) states that “public authorities will promote conditions for the free and effective participation of youth in the political, social, economic and cultural development” in its article 48, therefore, public authorities must develop youth policies as it has been done for the last forty years. However, the Constitution does not include a section stating youth policies and so, in order to address this lack of specific assignment, the different Autonomous Regions assumed exclusive responsibility in their own Statutes.

In this way there is no General Government Administration Youth Comprehensive Law but a variety of different plans seeking to coordinate political performances. In February 2017, the Secretary of State for Social Services and Equality announced the preparation of the Second Action Plan of the Youth Strategy 2017-2020. The **Youth Strategy 2020** (Estrategia Juventud 2020) is currently in force, approved by the Council of Ministers on the 12th of September 2014. This Strategy goes together with the first Action Plan 2014-2016 (Plan de Acción 2014-2016) and the Second Action Plan 2017-2020, establishing axes of action, goals, measures and budget for this period. Besides these Plans, there is an ordinary budget for the Youth Promotion and Services from the Ministry of Health, Consumption and Social Welfare.

Although most of the actions related to youth are carried out through the Autonomous Regions and local bodies, on a national scale the decision-taking structure is related to the Spanish Youth Institute (Instituto de la Juventud (**INJUVE**)) and the Youth Interministerial Commission. Coordination of the authorities with the associative youth movement is made through the Spanish Youth Council (**Consejo de la Juventud de España**).

Young People in Spain

Ratio of young people in the total population on 1st January

Ratio of men and women in the youth population

Ratio of young immigrants in all immigrants from non-EU countries

Total number of young people:

7 037 670

References:

Ratio (%) of young people in the total population (2018): Eurostat, yth_demo_020 [data extracted on 13/01/2020].

Absolute number of young people on 1 January for the age group 15-29 (2018): Eurostat, yth_demo_010 [data extracted on 13/01/2020].

Ratio (%) of men and women in the youth population (2018): Eurostat, yth_demo_020 [data extracted on 13/01/2020].

Young immigrants from non-EU countries (2017): Eurostat, yth_demo_070 [data extracted on 13/01/2020].

The youth population in Spain (between 15 and 29 years old) represents about 15% of the population, with a distribution between men and women slightly higher than for women (1% more than men).

In the case of the immigrant population, the percentage of young people increases significantly and represents about one third of the total number of immigrants. The data is interesting because it directly involves youth policies relating to the social inclusion of this part of young foreigners both in education and in employment.

From the statistics of the last decades, in the last 10 years¹, the reduction in the number and proportion of young people has been remarkably accelerated.

The data indicate that if it were not for the demographic contributions of immigration, an acceptable demographic bonus would not be guaranteed for the youth cohorts of the 2010/2020 period. In any case, even with the demographically positive increase in immigration, the inevitable shortage of young people in the coming years in Spain represents a challenge that must be faced with determination.

Regarding the political measures provided for in the Youth Strategy 2020, of interest for the INGAME project, it is observed that a specific axis has been proposed dedicated to "Participation, volunteering, coexistence and inclusion and equality", which aims to address the following actions:

- Promote the channels and tools to increase the participation and volunteering of young associates and non-associates, especially those linked to ICT.
- Fight against the social exclusion of the most disadvantaged sectors of the youth population.
- Promotion of equality.

Youth policies and civic engagement

The **Youth Strategy 2020** ([Estrategia Juventud 2020](#), approved by the Council of Ministers, 12 September 2014) is the document currently in force that serves as a reference to youth policies that are developed in Spain. This Strategy aims to promote policies and services for young people that affect areas such as employment, participation, youth associations, volunteering, leisure and free time, healthy lifestyle habits, prevention, values for coexistence, etc. and to foster the collaboration of the set of ministerial departments and public administrations whose actions affect youth.

According to the Diagnosis on the situation and opinions of Youth in Spain contained in the document, in relation to civic engagement (p.31), the articulation of the forms of social and political participation of young people occurs mainly through voting. It is the only action that stands out in percentage terms for a majority of the group, taken globally, which rises to 63% in age groups over 18 years of age. Apart from voting, between 23% and 30% of youth say they have participated in a strike (27%), signed protest petitions (26%) and participated in authorized demonstrations (22%). The rest of the

¹ INE. Instituto Nacional de Estadística.

https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/es/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176951&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735572981

proposed actions are clearly a minority, in all cases carried out by less than 15% of the young group, including actions for the exchange of information and / or debate via the web, mobile phone or email.

In recent years, there has been an increase in voting, participation in strikes, petition signatures, product boycotts, and to a lesser extent in illegal protest activities, collaboration with organizations and attendance at authorized demonstrations.

In particular, the survey on “Young People, Participation and Political Culture” of 2017 (Injuve 2017) shows that young people are increasingly interested in politics in Spain: 37% declare they feel a lot or a lot of interest and this figure increases study after study. In this sense, politics is increasingly a topic of conversation among young people and their families (63%), friends (50%) and colleagues from work or studies (40%).

The tools that young people use to find out about current events have evolved from traditional and mass media such as television, press or radio and, currently, one in two young people in Spain uses the Internet as their primary source of information. And four out of ten, it is reported mainly through social networks.

It is worth highlighting the incorporation of **virtual methods of political participation** (forums and discussions on the internet, sending or exchanging messages via mobile phone or email ...).

Gender equality

Source: Injuve (2008), Jóvenes e Igualdad de género

Equality between women and men appears among the social objectives desirable for young people in Spain: the vast majority consider that such equality makes society fairer and facilitates personal development.

GRÁFICO 2

Modelo ideal de familia

Fuente: INJUVE, Sondeo de Opinión 2008.

The number of young people is also the majority who indicate as an ideal family model that based on the equality of roles and functions around the family environment, inside and outside the home. The majority of young women have not perceived discrimination in the different social spheres in which they operate, although it should be noted that some discrimination regarding equality still persists in our society.

GRÁFICO 3

Discriminaciones sufridas por ser mujer

Fuente: INJUVE, Sondeo de Opinión 2008.

Gender violence appears as the most undesirable scenario in relations between men and women. In the country, this type of violence appears as a social problem that generates a considerable number

of victims among the female collective. Spanish youth openly reject sexist or gender violence, as well as the different manifestations of violence.

Fuente: INJUVE, Sondeo de Opinión 2008.

Social inclusion

We are living in times of change and of cultural, social, economic and political alterations unparalleled in the history of humanity. These are transformations that, hand in hand with ICT and technoscience, have surprisingly occurred in Western adult societies and, in a particularly disconcerting way, in developing countries. The impact of these technologies has been producing greater or lesser changes in large fundamental sectors of the socio-political and economic structure of a society: education, culture, the media, the business world, the economy..., even politics.

These are changes and transformations that have a very special impact on the young population who find themselves with a real environment of their lives and the context of their concerns and opportunities significantly different from the society of previous generations. In fact, we are witnessing the advent of the First Globalized Young Generation, of which the phenomenon and, above all, its consequences cannot yet be assessed. They are the so-called 'digital natives' (also known by various other names), who were born from the beginning of the 90s.

In this itinerary it can already be seen how the vital and cultural differences between young people in any part of the planet are tending to an evident homogenization, as a result of this sudden impact of ICT and as a consequence of the rapid spread of information, communication and knowledge through the Internet and social networks.

In this context, it is encouraging to see that, in the face of so much change, the altruistic ideal is still compatible with these times of pragmatism and accelerated technological changes. The Youth Observatory (Observatorio INJUVE) already sees the possibility that concepts such as 'collective intelligence' and 'collaborative intelligence' are making their way among young people with more intensity and formalization than ever. Especially for young people, while spatial, temporal and cultural distances are shortened, the perception of the need for ethical, coexistence and caring for the planet increases.

2.2. Good Practices

Youth and ICT

Youth Strategy 2020 (p.33) analyses the new global approach to the ICT issue among Youth.

Spain is a country with a strong immersion in the use and consumption of ICT² and the school system has (in particular public centers) significant technological investments.

Most of the young people, the youngest, already belong to a generation of digital natives, who do not need to be trained in new technologies so that they can be competent users of them. Their capacity, not only to use ICTs on a daily basis but to give them new uses and even transform them, is very similar to that of young people in the countries that are leading the digital and technological revolution.

However, it is necessary to fight against the emergence of digital divides. Culture and digital knowledge have been widely implanted among Spanish youth. According to the EJE / LB2011, only 2.3% of young people use the internet at school, university or a library, perhaps because 91.8% do so regularly from home and the rest at work. This data portrays their mere condition of dependent users, which implies that the country has a certain deficit in the professional, educational and employment use of ICT. In this sense, the main need is not to reach more users but to have more innovative and creative young people in the field of ICT. Because, although ICTs are instruments for life, they are also instruments for work, social and labor insertion, entrepreneurship and creativity.

² It is significant that the activity that most young people practice is to use a computer and other telematic devices (93.1%), even before socializing with friends (83.9%). Source: Estrategia Juventud 2020, p. 29.

Among the most significant initiatives undertaken to give more options to young people as actors and not just receivers of technology from different perspectives (professional, social, leisure and free time ...), we note the **INNGAMES program**. It is an INJUVE program (<http://www.injuve.es/noticia/se-prepara-inngames-2015>) aimed at promoting and consolidating the culture of entrepreneurship, employability, training and innovation in the field of new technologies, especially in the creation of software in the field of video games among young people who wish to undertake and who have not completed their secondary school studies or are of post-compulsory education age. There have been two editions of the program, in 2014 and 2015.

Youth and Videogames

About videogames, their inseparable relationship with the youth age groups, make these products required in the study of youth subcultures. But at the same time, their ability to transmit messages and models makes them vehicles of socialization, sources of identity and texts from which to learn.

How much time do young people in Spain spend on video games? In what type of support do they consume them? What are your favorite products and why? How do you understand the relationship between television and network of networks? What are the most valued dimensions of fiction of which they are followers and followers? What kinds of rewards do they find in their role as gamers? According to the research of Mar Chicharro Merayo in *Revista de estudios de juventud* 106. *La juventud en la pantalla* (2014), in 2012, 67.8% of young people confessed their fondness and liking for the use of consoles and video games, showing a growing interest compared to previous years. From the game support point of view, the data collected show how portable devices prevail in the surveyed group compared to the more classic formula of the video console, in very clear connection with the growing increase in mobile devices used by the bulk of the population. However, video game consumption is much lower than television consumption and is especially concentrated on weekends. In any of the cases, the relationship that the player establishes with the game is quite different depending on their objectives and interests, as well as their attitude. Hence the distinction, between achievers, killers, socializers and explorers. Thus, for example, and in the case of online role-playing video games (MUDs, multi-user-dungeon), when choosing between the “world” and the players, priority can be given to their relationship with other users (socializers and killers), or you can choose to interact with the game itself (explorers, achievers). In the dichotomy between action and interaction, there are those who prefer to influence the game, or other players (killers, achievers), while others choose interaction over action (socializers, explorers).

Serious games in education for equality between young people

The special relevance of serious games, as a type of video games whose purpose is not exclusively entertainment, has become increasingly popular in a wide group of professional sectors (education, health, defense, information, etc.) and has received, in recent years, significant academic attention in Spain. As examples of serious games for empowerment and equality awareness of genre, Salvador Gómez García in *Revista de estudios de juventud* 106, analyses two products: Wonder City (NBC, 2013) and Half the Sky Movement: The Game (Frima Studio, 2013).

3. Research results: questionnaires

3.1 Findings from field-based research

This section presents the findings of the field work conducted during the research and data collection for the report. The presentation of the findings will be structured according to the research actions taken with participants in the field research (i.e., young persons aged 18-35, the relevant stakeholders, and the questionnaire to the target group).

The first questionnaire (Q1) answered by six young people, four girls and two boys, 50% of them between 31 and 35 years old, all involved in study (1) or work activities (5).

The second questionnaire (Q2) addressed to project stakeholders. 6 persons answered members of Public Institutions and Social Services (4) and Youth training institutions (2). 50% of them aged between 46 and 55 years.

The third questionnaire (Q3) answered by 20 young people aged between 18 and 35, 18 women and 2 men.

3.1.2 Young Persons Aged 18-35

Based on the collective answers of the research question 5, the participants define civic engagement as social involvement through actions and projects that address public issues. There is a wide perspective about citizen awareness embracing not only the human community but also nature and environment. The sense of responsibility for the role that awaits young people is also present.

The role of education from the schools and institutions themselves is claimed (question 6) to promote social awareness and civic projects. The main issues to be addressed are adults' lives, coexistence,

worries about the economic, work and family situation. More opportunities in terms of travel facilities, active voice/voting, leadership are among the requests.

Young people point to coeducation initiatives in schools and cooperative social projects at local level as examples of intervention for promoting civic engagement and social inclusion (question 7) but, even if they underline in general the importance of these initiatives, one of them refers to the excessive bureaucracy of the initiatives associated with the low interest of young people.

They require practical applications based on real data, but acknowledge they have not direct experience on the use of ICT as approach to social inclusion or gender equality (question 8). An opinion on serious games explains that their characteristics do not generate motivation or direct interest of young people (“Many times serious games are developed that nobody would play of their own free will”) despite approaches such as gamification or game-based learning can help address issues of gender, inclusion or situations related to the SDGs

Attractive stories that engage the player, for the player to feel identified with some important character, in some feature, be it physical, cultural or attitudinal, virtual reality, real contexts are the main features the INGAME game should have. Nevertheless, they are aware that there are many types of players, and the same game is not for everyone.

3.1.3 Group 2: Stakeholders

The factors influencing the civic engagement of young adults (question 4) based on the frequency of answers of the participants are as follow: education, social relationships, young adult context, previous training and family environment and economic level, culture, interpersonal relationships, personality. On the other hand, the individualistic need for money, successful and recognition contrasts with factors as solidarity and equality.

Similarly to young people, speaking of kind of activities to be delivered to increase the participation of young people in public life (question 5), stakeholders identify education as the main context for actions (education at all levels and in different modalities - seminars and webinars with experts of the field...

The main difficulties stakeholders face in involving young people in civic engagement activities (question 6) are as follow: (a) lack of interest; (b) lack of maturity; (c) lack of time; (d) lack of motivation; (e) lack of utility; (f) a gape in civic values.

Joint actions, roundtables, campaigns are example of initiatives aimed to improve the civic participation of young people, but the stakeholders don't provide specific evidences (question 7). Two respondents don't know of other initiatives.

Based on participants' answers (question 8), digital and online technologies are considered a very important factor in attracting and engaging young people to issues of active citizenship and discussing issues of international interest. The contribution of digital social media and other innovative approaches such as online gaming, serious games, game-based Learning can also very useful for younger ages. All the stakeholders interviewed use these technologies in particular they have experience of virtual reality in education and use of mobile learning technologies to improve communication and social behaviour of students.

About the INGAME proposal, the game should be (question 9) (a) open, (b) available in a mobile device, (c) visible in different browser, (d) collaborative, (e) count on engaging elements (speak the young language, consider learning as an added value). As regard the storytelling, the game should present real situations, not abstract situations, and the young people should apply social respect rules to their close people, close environments. Only one person refers to public recognition and rewards as a requirement of the game.

Only a further suggestion has been proposed: remove generational barriers by making the game designed and disseminated by young people themselves. It is an interesting proposal, in line with the strategy defined in the document Youth Strategy 2020 (p.33) about the approach to the ICT issue among Youth described above at 2.2 Good Practices.

3.1.4 Group 3: Target Group

Based on the collection of the overall answers of the young people interviewed (20 participants), the term of civic engagement (question 5) is defined in terms of responsibility, respect and engagement with the community and the environment.

The group seems quite active as regard the participation in initiatives to support civic and social issues (question 6):

There were involved in particular in initiatives about (question 7): Marches against terrorism (4), Gender violence (7), Environment (2), Human rights (2). Topics identified only by a person were: independence of Catalonia, bullfighting abolition, racism, food collection, charity concerts, against health cuts, etter public service, social education.

Regarding the role of technology in promoting social inclusion and equal participation (question 8), they agree in general on the positive contribution of internet and social media, even if some concern is present about the equal access to technology and the risks of the online interaction. On the other hand, they are not so much informed about game-based learning initiatives or other initiatives on young people civic engagement (15 of them) (questions 9 and 10).

Opinions about gamification (question 11) are partially positive, but 7 persons don't provide suggestions to their use to enhance critical reflection on social and political circumstances. Someone is skeptical and find hard to conceive that gamification can help people think critically or consider that the "gamification" concept is not in line with the educational value because of the competitive element of the games.

Suggestions of successful activities (question 12) are competitions of different kinds as well as theater and debates, photographs, marches and documentaries, workshops, laboratories, games, exhibitions, round tables, advertisement campaigns, social media campaigns and sport

Most of respondents didn't provided additional notes (15 of them). Other suggestions provide on one hand a positive message of solidarity encouraging young people on helping others and trying to be better persons with other people and nature, but on the other hand it is present the fear of the consequences of technological consumerism.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

4.1. Key results of research

Young people are seen as a resource and an active potential for the social development of the country. At the political level, youth issues and needs are taken into consideration and at the same time the desire to collaborate and be useful in the social field is perceived in young people.

From recent studies positive values of solidarity and civic commitment emerge which are also confirmed by the small survey developed in the project. There is a demand for concrete initiatives, even if it seems that young people in general do not receive sufficient information through their communication channels (they are not proactive or do not have examples of good practices or specific activities by hand). On some occasions there is pessimism regarding the youth response (lack of time, interest ...) and they see many dangers in the digital world (individualism, risks in online interaction ...)

4.2. Recommendations for future action (always in relation to INGAME's aims)

In particular we should take in account all the comments about the features of the game, both from the technical point of view (open, accessible...) and from perspective of the narration, of the characters, of adherence to real life without giving up the playful element.

It also seems necessary to invest in training and dissemination, appropriately selecting the communication channels and the language used by young people, so that the initiative and the message really reach the target audience.

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6. Annexes

Evaluation grid: questionnaire 1 (target group)		
Partner	University of Salamanca	
Age profile of the participants (please insert the number of people belonging to each age / age group)	<p>_____ 18-20 <u>2</u> 21-25</p> <p><u>1</u> 26-30 <u>3</u> 31-35</p>	
Number of participants and their gender split	<p>Females: 4</p> <p>Males: 2</p>	
In minimum 2 pages and maximum 4 pages:		
Question n°	Common theme	Contrasting findings
5. What does civic engagement mean to you?	<p>All kind of social involvement through actions and projects that address public issues.</p> <p>Becoming an active part of your community.</p> <p>To have citizen awareness in a broad sense, not only towards people but also towards the environment.</p>	<p>The responsibility that the individuals that make up a society should have with their society</p>
6. What kind of activities do you think should be delivered to increase the participation of young adult in public life in general and more specifically, their civic engagement?	<p>To address issues like adults' lives, their coexistence, their worries about the economic, work and family situation.</p> <p>To promote social awareness and civic projects through education from the schools and institutions themselves.</p> <p>To have more opportunities, travel facilities, active voice/voting, leadership</p>	<p>Education in social values must also address a correct information literacy to allow civic engagement to be based on real data / situations.</p> <p>Activities to protect the environment and save resources.</p>

<p>7. Do you know any policies, practices and interventions for promoting young civic engagement, social inclusion and gender equality? If so, should they improve or change?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - co-education in schools from a gender perspective. - cooperative social projects at local level to work for the social inclusion of excluded. 	<p>The interventions are mainly bureaucratic and most of the students have no interest.</p> <p>Improving the actual situation is positive, particularly starting from concrete situations.</p> <p>A respondent doesn't know any activity to indicate.</p>
<p>8. Are you aware of new technologies (digital tools and mobile devices like GPS, PDAs, Tablet PCs, Virtual Reality, handheld technologies, mobile learning technologies, etc.) and innovative approaches (like for example Online Gaming, Serious Games, Game-based Learning) that can be used to discuss global issues, like social inclusion and gender equality? If yes, have you ever used them and why?</p>	<p>5 respondents know the topic, but they haven't direct experience on it.</p>	<p>One experience on serious games in EU training.</p> <p>Many times serious games are developed that nobody would play of their own free will, which loses the pedagogical sense of the use of games in learning.</p> <p>Knowledge of 3D or virtual reality to transport and involve the audience in certain realities.</p>
<p>9. We are developing an online game, called INGAME which will allow users to learn from simulated experience enhancing critical reflection on social and political circumstances, build skills and stimulate interest for collective action. What would an online game like INGAME need to attract your interest? Which features would you like the game to have?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Feeling involved in a real context - Collaborative game where decision making is based on communication and understanding of the other people you are playing online with. - the game should integrate narrative characteristics, this is, attractive stories that engage the player, and it would be relevant for the player to feel identified with some important character, for which similarity would be important in some feature, be it physical, cultural or attitudinal. - virtual reality can help 	<p>There are many types of players, and the same game is not for everyone.</p> <p>Many games can be targeted to learning depending on their use.</p> <p>Players don't read and listen unless that's part of the game.</p> <p>A respondent doesn't suggest features.</p>

	<p>narrative transport, but it should not be abused, or the result may be the opposite, and cause rejection.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Easy use, active, attractive design, lots of options 	
<p>10. Do you have additional notes or suggestions that you think could be useful for our research?</p>	<p>The line between a playable game and something you would only use if forced, is a very fine one.</p> <p>Really interesting and innovative initiative.</p>	

Evaluation grid: questionnaire 2 (stakeholders)

Partner	University of Salamanca	
Age profile of the participants <i>(please insert the number of people belonging to each age / age group)</i>	19-25 years <input type="checkbox"/> 36-45 years: 1 Above 55 years: 1	26-35 years: 1 46-55 years: 3
Number of participants and their gender split	Females: 4	Males: 2
In minimum 2 pages and maximum 4 pages:		
Question n°	Common theme	Contrasting findings
4. Which factors influence the civic engagement of young adult?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Education, social relationships and young adults context. - Previous training and family environment. - Economic level, culture, interpersonal relationships, personality. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Money? successful? recognition? - Solidarity and equality
5. What kind of activities do you think should be delivered to increase the participation of young adult in public life in general and more specifically, their civic engagement?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Include this concepts at all educational levels, seminars and webinars with experts of the field, events were the young adults can develop a civil behaviour. - Public services. - Education in values. - Providing different forms of participation, playful activities included. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - If someone has an interest in engaging in actions to improve their own context, but does not have enough initiative, it is necessary that the spaces, the initiatives, reach them, instead of having to go looking for them. - rewards and recognition, maybe future personal improvement.
6. What are the main difficulties you face in involving young people in civic engagement activities?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of interest, maturity. - Time, motivation, utility. - Individualism. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A gape in civic values. - Not all young people are interested.

<p>7. In your area of work, do you know of successful initiatives aimed to improve civic participation of young people and their attention to social inclusion or gender equality issues? If so, which are the main elements of success?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In cities the different initiatives have a good response, people attending to seminars, asking questions, looking for resources or participating in initiatives. The problem is how to engage people from villages with other kind of sociocultural contexts. - joint actions, roundtables, campaigns. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Two respondents don't know of other initiatives.
<p>8. Are you aware of new technologies (digital tools and mobile devices like GPS, PDAs, Tablet PCs, Virtual Reality, hand-held technologies, mobile learning technologies, etc.) and innovative approaches (like for example Online Gaming, Serious Games, Game-based Learning) that can be used to discuss global issues, like social inclusion and gender equality? If yes, have you ever used them and why?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All the respondents are aware of it and use them with their students. - In particular they use: Virtual reality in Education and mobile learning technologies to improve communication and social behaviour of students. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -
<p>9. We are developing an online game, called INGAME which will allow users to learn from simulated experience enhancing critical reflection on social and political circumstances, build</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It should be open, it should be available in a mobile device, it should be visible in different browsers - Engaging elements - To present real situations, not abstract situations, and the young people should apply social respect rules to their close people, close environments. - Gameplay. learning is an added 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public Recognition and rewards

<p>skills and stimulate interest for collective action. What would an online game like INGAME need to attract your interest? Which features would you like the game to have?</p>	<p>value.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collaborative game would be the most appropriate for the theme. - Speak the young language 	
<p>10. Do you have additional notes or suggestions that you think could be useful for our research?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Remove generational barriers by making the game designed and disseminated by young people themselves 	<p>4 respondents don't add notes 1 is interested to be informed of the results.</p>

Evaluation grid: questionnaire 3 (target group)		
Partner	University of Salamanca	
Age profile of the participants (please insert the number of people belonging to each age / age group)	<u>7</u> 18-20 <u>5</u> 21-25 <u>1</u> 26-30 <u>7</u> 31-35 >35: 0	
Number of participants in and their gender split	Females: 18 Males: 2	
In minimum 2 pages and maximum 4 pages:		
Question n°	Common theme	Contrasting findings
5. What does civic engagement mean to you?	A "responsibility" to change or at least try to change the things that you think are wrong. Being a good person and helping others. Respect for people and the environment. Engagement with community.	I don't know (1) For me it is closely related to social engineering (1) To vote and meet civic standards (1) No answer (1)
6. Have you participated in any of these initiatives in the last two years?	Square demonstrations, marches, sit-in (11) Petitions (4) None of these (3) Awareness campaigns on social networks (2)	
7. What was the cause?	Marches against terrorism (4) Gender violence (7) Environment (2) Human rights (2)	Independence of Catalonia (1) Bullfighting abolition (1) Racism (1) Food collection (1) Charity concerts (1) Against health cuts (1) Better public service (1) Social Education (1) Nothing

<p>8.</p> <p>Do you think that technology could play a role in promoting social inclusion and equal participation? If yes, how? If not, why not?</p>	<p>Yes, because (16):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - internet is powerful and can be use for changing - technology supports social inclusion by social media and videogames - by mean of technology you can reach more people and create a greater impact on society - Social networking sites have been helping to spread the voices of minorities. 	<p>No, because (3):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - access to technology generates social inequalities. - the interaction could generate problems <p>No answer (1)</p> <p>Yes, because of possibility of translations</p>
<p>9.</p> <p>Are you aware of game-based learning initiatives? If so, could you name these? what do you think?</p>	<p>NO: 15</p> <p>YES 5:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Games to learn languages or children's games. - Cooperative Learning – Montessori. 	<p>Games are beneficial both for the academic results of the student and their motivation towards the subject.</p> <p>Furthermore, cooperative games can be an interesting tool to promote healthy group dynamics, and, of course, social inclusion.</p> <p>Such kind of initiatives always sounds distant as to possible implementation.</p> <p>it's a way to attract people who may not be interested in other formats.</p>
<p>10.</p> <p>Do you know of any initiatives on young people's civic engagement you consider 'best practices'? If yes, name them.</p>	<p>NO: 15</p> <p>YES: 5 Campaigns through Instagram; camps; Volunteering; helping people with illnesses; foundations; foster houses; pick garbage up of beaches and natural parks</p>	<p>I follow accounts of institutions that fit my tastes and support initiatives that seem appropriate to me, such as pacma, international amnesty, or greenpeace.</p> <p>Working for righteous, good-willed ONGs and other sorts of aid organizations are probably the best way to make a change on people's lives; and, though I don't really participate much on public manifestations (since I tend to consider them overly noisy and, sometimes, vaguely meaningful), I am positive that they contribute to spread awareness on unjust situations.</p>

<p>11. How do you think Gamification could be used to enhance critical reflection on social and political circumstances of young adult?</p>	<p>No answer (7)</p> <p>Yes, by role playing games; in a equalitary way where everybody would be included and with out prejudices; making visibility campaigns about social and political problems; in a ludic way.</p>	<p>I find it hard to conceive that gamification can help people think critically.</p> <p>I think everything can be quite helpful if you can get there in the right way.</p> <p>I think the “gamification” concept is a mistake to education so the main value of this concept is the individual competitive.</p>
<p>12. According to you what are the most successful activities and practices for fostering civic participation, social inclusion and gender equality among young people (i.e. diversity-days with games, workshops, exhibitions, theatre, round-tables/debates, competitions on drawings, photographs, etc.)?</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Differently according to the recipient. - Any activity that is entertaining and teaches without forcing, better if participatory. - is crucial that every activity is sensibly planned and doesn't drive “off track” from the main purpose. - Interesting free activities.
<p>13. Do you have additional notes or suggestions that you think could be useful for our research?</p>	<p>Most of respondents didn't provided additional notes. (No answer 11; NO 5)</p> <p>We should encourage mostly young people on helping others and trying to be better persons with other people and nature.</p> <p>To teach children the consequences arising from these behaviors of technological consumerism.</p>	<p>Nowadays it is more complicated to time to think in social civic initiatives.</p>

INGAME

Gaming for Social Inclusion and Civic Participation